

STUDY OF THE BIOMORPHOLOGY OF THE PROMISING *ARCTIUM NEMOROSUM* PLANT

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ABSTRACT

Arctium nemorosum, a popular medicinal plant, which is widely used both in traditional medicine and in modern scientific medicine. Plant preparations are promising for use in therapeutic, oncological, and neurological practice. Biomorphology, ecology and medicinal properties of *Arctium nemorosum* belonging to the Asteraceae family are discussed. Information about the use of ancient and modern plants in traditional and scientific medicine is given.

INTRODUCTION

Many wild and cultivated species of medicinal plants grow, develop and yield in Uzbekistan. They can be used in the fight against a number of diseases. In accordance with this, the production of medicinal raw materials on an industrial scale based on the cultivation of wild medicinal plants that grow in different soil and climate conditions, the development of agrotechnics for their cultivation is the current demand [1]. Medicinal plants are of great importance in nature and human life. The effect of medicinal plants on the body depends on the amount of chemical compounds in their composition. These compounds accumulate in vegetative and generative organs of plants. The necessary parts of the plants for the preparation of medicine are collected at different times.

Biennial herbaceous plant 1 to 2.5 m high. Powerful rhizome. The stem is branched, rough, covered with short hairs. Leaves petiolate, arranged alternately. The shape of the leaf plate is broadly ovoid, heart-shaped-finely toothed. The lower surface of the leaf is white-grayish in color, pubescent [4].

Inflorescences - large baskets with a diameter of 3-4 cm, surrounded by rather long, slightly pubescent bracts. The upper flowers are grouped in the form of glomeruli, the lower ones are located singly on short pedicels. Corolla purplish red. Flowering occurs from July to September [3,4].

The fruits are achenes 6-8 mm long, obovate, slightly ribbed in the longitudinal direction, light gray-brown in color with dark spots. At the end of the achene there is a tuft 2.5-3 mm long [3][4].

Fig 1: General view and flower of *Arctium nemorosum*

Scandinavia, Atlantic, Central and Eastern Europe, Caucasus. In Belarus, it is found in insular habitats beyond the northeastern border of continuous distribution. Locations are known in the Pruzhany district of the Brest region., Vitebsk district, Vitebsk region, Grodno and Svisloch districts of the Grodno region. and Mstislavsky district, Mogilev region.

Anthropogenic - economic transformation of lands (cutting forests for the main use, destruction of the ground cover, burning grass, excessive recreational loads); natural - hybridization with synanthropic species of the genus, displacement by more competitive species (due to strong shading). Blooms in July - August. Entomophile. Seeds ripen in August - September. Zoochore (epizoochore). Propagated exclusively by seeds.

Found throughout most of Europe [5,6]. It grows in broad-leaved forests, in forest glades, in coastal thickets of alder, sometimes along roadsides [4]. The plant is considered a rare species in Finland, the Baltic states, Belarus and Ukraine [7]. In Russia, only isolated cases of growth have been noted [2].

Arctium nemorosum plants are listed in the Red Books of the following countries: Finland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Belarus. In Ukraine, the plant is included in the Red Books of the Lviv and Khmelnytsky regions, in Russia - in the Red Books of the Kaluga region and the Republic of Tatarstan [7].

Summary: Taking into account that special attention is being paid to the protection, cultivation and processing of medicinal plants belonging to the local flora in Uzbekistan, to the development of the preparation of natural medicines, we also study the medicinal properties of the *Arctium nemorosum* plant, this naturally growing plant Researches are being carried out on the cultivation of the plant, the expansion of its cultivation and the development of agrotechnics of its cultivation.

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